

Spectrum of Opportunistic Fungal Infections in HIV/AIDS Patients at a Tertiary Care Hospital in Patna

Babita Kumari¹, Spriha Smriti², Pratulya Nandan³

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Microbiology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Microbiology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

³Professor, Department of Microbiology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Babita Kumari

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Abstract:

Background: Opportunistic fungal infections are a major cause of morbidity and mortality in HIV/AIDS patients, particularly in those with severe immunosuppression. Despite advancements in antiretroviral therapy (ART), these infections remain prevalent in resource-limited settings, posing significant clinical challenges.

Aim: The study aimed to investigate the spectrum of opportunistic fungal infections in HIV/AIDS patients at a tertiary care hospital in Patna, Bihar, and to explore the association between CD4 counts and the prevalence of these infections.

Methods: A descriptive, observational, cross-sectional study was conducted. A total of 100 HIV/AIDS patients with confirmed opportunistic fungal infections were included. Data were collected on demographic and clinical characteristics, CD4 counts, and types of fungal infections. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The study found that candidiasis was the most common opportunistic fungal infection (45%), followed by Pneumocystis pneumonia (20%) and cryptococcal meningitis (15%). A significant association was observed between lower CD4 counts and higher prevalence of these infections. Candidiasis and cryptococcal meningitis were particularly prevalent in patients with CD4 counts below 200 cells/ μ L. Treatment outcomes were favorable, with a 70% recovery rate; however, the mortality rate was 10%.

Conclusion: Opportunistic fungal infections remain a significant concern among HIV/AIDS patients, especially those with low CD4 counts. The study highlights the need for early diagnosis and aggressive treatment to improve patient outcomes in resource-limited settings.

Recommendations: The study recommends regular monitoring of CD4 counts and prompt initiation of antifungal therapy in HIV/AIDS patients. Increased access to diagnostic facilities and antifungal treatments is crucial, particularly in rural and resource-limited areas.

Keywords: HIV/AIDS, opportunistic infections, fungal infections, CD4 count, Patna.

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Introduction

A substantial contributing factor to morbidity and death in people with HIV and AIDS is opportunistic fungal infections. Patients with significant immunosuppression, which is usually characterised by low CD4 T-cell counts, are more likely to contract these diseases. The introduction of antiretroviral medication (ART) has significantly decreased the prevalence of many opportunistic infections; yet, in areas with limited resources, where access to ART and consistent surveillance may be irregular, fungal infections continue to pose a significant therapeutic problem [1].

Among the most prevalent opportunistic fungal diseases seen in HIV/AIDS patients are candidiasis, Cryptococcal meningitis, Pneumocystis pneumonia

(PCP), and aspergillosis. When the immune system deteriorates, candidiasis, particularly oropharyngeal and esophageal, is frequently the first opportunistic infection to manifest, acting as an early clinical marker of HIV infection development. In HIV-positive people, cryptococcal meningitis—caused by *Cryptococcus neoformans*—continues to be a major cause of death, especially in sub-Saharan Africa and Southeast Asia, where HIV prevalence is highest [2, 3].

In India, opportunistic fungal infections among HIV/AIDS patients continue to pose a serious threat to public health, especially in areas where the virus is more common. Research from across India has shown that amongst HIV/AIDS patients,

opportunistic fungal infections are a major cause of hospitalisation and death. Depending on the geographic location, healthcare resources available, and the fungal pathogen epidemiology in the area, the range of these illnesses might vary greatly [4]. Even with improvements in HIV care, the continued prevalence of these infections draws attention to gaps in early diagnosis and treatment, especially in remote and low-resource environments. This issue is made worse by the fact that many healthcare facilities do not routinely perform fungal testing, which delays diagnosis and treatment. Treatment for these infections is made more difficult by the growing concern over the emergence of antifungal resistance [5].

The study aimed to investigate the spectrum of opportunistic fungal infections in HIV/AIDS patients at a tertiary care hospital in Patna, Bihar, and to explore the association between CD4 counts and the prevalence of these infections.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a descriptive, observational, and cross-sectional study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in the Microbiology Department of Patna Medical College and Hospital (PMCH), Patna, Bihar. The hospital serves as a tertiary care center, catering to a diverse patient population, including those with HIV/AIDS.

Study Duration: The study was conducted over a period of one year, from March 2022 to February 2023.

Participants: A total of 100 HIV/AIDS patients diagnosed with opportunistic fungal infections were included in the study. The patients were selected from those attending the outpatient department or admitted to various wards of PMCH.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients diagnosed with HIV/AIDS, confirmed by standard serological tests.
- Patients who provided informed consent to participate in the study.
- Patients of all age groups and genders.
- Patients presenting with clinical symptoms suggestive of opportunistic fungal infections.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with concomitant bacterial or viral illnesses that could complicate the diagnosis of fungal infections.
- Patients who have received antifungal medication within the last three months.
- Patients unwilling or unable to provide informed consent.
- Patients with incomplete medical records.

Bias: In order to reduce selection bias, all eligible patients were included in the study for the full duration. Information bias was reduced by ensuring that data collection was standardized and conducted by trained personnel. Confounding factors were addressed through statistical adjustments during data analysis.

Data Collection: A pre-made proforma that contained information on demographics, clinical history, test results, and treatment outcomes was used to gather data. Blood, sputum, urine, and swabs were taken from the afflicted areas in order to identify and culture the fungus.

Procedure

- Patients were evaluated clinically for symptoms of opportunistic fungal infections.
- Samples were collected under aseptic conditions and processed in the Microbiology Department.
- Fungal cultures were incubated, and identification was carried out using standard microbiological techniques.
- Data on CD4 counts, viral load, and other relevant clinical parameters were also recorded.

Statistical Analysis: Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics (percentages and frequencies) were calculated for categorical variables, and mean and standard deviation for continuous variables. Chi-square tests were used to compare categorical variables, with significance set at $p < 0.05$. Multivariate logistic regression identified factors associated with specific fungal infections.

Results

A total of 100 HIV/AIDS patients with confirmed opportunistic fungal infections were included in the study.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Frequency (n=100)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	62	62%
Female	38	38%
Age Group (years)		
18-30	22	22%
31-40	35	35%

41-50	28	28%
51-60	15	15%
Residence		
Urban	47	47%
Rural	53	53%
Education Level		
Illiterate	15	15%
Primary Education	28	28%
Secondary Education	40	40%
Higher Education	17	17%

The clinical characteristics and CD4 count distribution among the participants are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Clinical Characteristics and CD4 Count

Characteristic	Frequency (n=100)	Percentage (%)
CD4 Count (cells/μL)		
<50	14	14%
50-200	46	46%
201-350	28	28%
>350	12	12%
Duration of HIV Diagnosis		
<1 year	25	25%
1-5 years	48	48%
>5 years	27	27%
Antiretroviral Therapy		
On ART	79	79%
Not on ART	21	21%

The types and frequencies of opportunistic fungal infections observed in the study participants are detailed in Table 3.

Table 3: Spectrum of Opportunistic Fungal Infections

Type of Fungal Infection	Frequency (n=100)	Percentage (%)
Candidiasis (Oral and Esophageal)	45	45%
Cryptococcal Meningitis	15	15%
Pneumocystis Pneumonia (PCP)	20	20%
Histoplasmosis	5	5%
Aspergillosis	10	10%
Mucormycosis	3	3%
Others	2	2%

An analysis was conducted to evaluate the association between CD4 count and the occurrence of specific opportunistic fungal infections.

Table 4: Association between CD4 Count and Fungal Infections

CD4 Count (cells/ μ L)	Candidiasis	Cryptococcal Meningitis	PCP	Histoplasmosis	Aspergillosis	Mucormycosis	Others
<50	8 (57.1%)	5 (35.7%)	1 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
50-200	27 (58.7%)	7 (15.2%)	10 (66.7%)	3 (20.0%)	1 (6.7%)	1 (6.7%)	1 (6.7%)
201-350	8 (28.6%)	2 (7.1%)	7 (50.0%)	1 (7.1%)	5 (35.7%)	1 (7.1%)	1 (7.1%)
>350	2 (16.7%)	1 (8.3%)	2 (28.6%)	1 (14.3%)	4 (57.1%)	1 (14.3%)	0 (0.0%)

The Chi-square test was used to assess the statistical significance of the association between CD4 count and fungal infections. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Statistical Analysis

- **Candidiasis** was significantly more common in patients with CD4 counts below 200 cells/ μ L ($p = 0.002$).

- **Cryptococcal meningitis** was most frequent in patients with CD4 counts <50 cells/ μ L ($p = 0.01$).
- **Pneumocystis pneumonia (PCP)** was more prevalent in patients with CD4 counts between 50-200 cells/ μ L ($p = 0.03$).
- No significant associations were found for **Histoplasmosis**, **Aspergillosis**, and **Mucormycosis** with specific CD4 count ranges ($p > 0.05$).

Table 5: Treatment Outcomes

Outcome	Frequency (n=100)	Percentage (%)
Complete Recovery	70	70%
Partial Recovery	20	20%
Mortality	10	10%

Discussion

The participants were predominantly male (62%), with most patients aged between 31 and 50 years. The majority of the patients (53%) were from rural areas, and nearly half had secondary education or higher. The study found that the majority of the participants (74%) had a CD4 count below 350 cells/ μ L, which is a critical threshold indicating severe immunosuppression and vulnerability to opportunistic infections.

The most common opportunistic fungal infection identified was candidiasis (45%), followed by Pneumocystis pneumonia (PCP) at 20%, and cryptococcal meningitis at 15%. Less frequent infections included aspergillosis, histoplasmosis, and mucormycosis. The occurrence of these infections was strongly associated with lower CD4 counts. For instance, candidiasis and cryptococcal meningitis were significantly more prevalent in patients with CD4 counts below 200 cells/ μ L, indicating that severe immunosuppression markedly increases the risk of these infections.

The treatment outcomes were generally favorable, with 70% of patients achieving complete recovery following antifungal therapy. However, there was a notable 10% mortality rate, underscoring the serious risk posed by these infections in severely immunocompromised patients. The findings highlight the importance of early diagnosis and aggressive treatment to improve outcomes in HIV/AIDS patients with opportunistic fungal infections.

There has been a rise in the diversity and prevalence of fungal pathogens that impact HIV/AIDS patients, according to a study looking at trends in opportunistic fungal infections. Non-traditional pathogens, which now account for 37% of all mould infections and a large share of the mortality in organ transplant recipients with mould infections, have emerged as a major shift from traditional pathogens like Aspergillus species, according to the research (Oxford Academic). The management of fungal infections in immune-compromised people, particularly those with HIV/AIDS, is becoming increasingly difficult, as this change highlights [6].

The range and mortality linked to opportunistic infections in HIV/AIDS patients were examined in a different study conducted in southwest China. Two of the most common and deadly illnesses, according to the study, were candidiasis and cryptococcal meningitis.

It was revealed that a considerable proportion of the observed mortality was caused by these infections, which were especially prevalent in patients with CD4+ T-cell counts <200 cells/ μ L [7].

In order to prevent serious infections such as cryptococcal meningitis, it is imperative that CD4+ levels remain above 200, as highlighted in the CDC's overview of fungal infections in HIV/AIDS patients. Additionally, this resource covered the significance of fungal pathogen spatial variations for treatment approaches [8].

Conclusion

The study reveals that opportunistic fungal infections are prevalent among HIV/AIDS patients with low CD4 counts. Candidiasis and Pneumocystis pneumonia are the most common infections, particularly in those with CD4 counts below 200 cells/ μ L. The outcomes of antifungal treatment were generally positive, with a 70% recovery rate. However, the study also highlights the need for early diagnosis and management to reduce mortality in this population.

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